

DIGITAL DESIRE IN CONSERVATIVE PAKISTAN: A USES AND GRATIFICATIONS STUDY OF DATING APPS

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Abstract

This study examines the uses and gratifications associated with mobile dating applications in Pakistan, a society where such practices intersect with deeply rooted patriarchal and conservative norms. Drawing on the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale (Welch & Morgan, 2018), the research investigates four primary gratifications: Validation, Relationships, Hook-Ups, and Entertainment. Given the sensitive and stigmatized nature of dating app use, data were collected through snowball sampling, resulting in 62 responses from users across multiple urban centers. Quantitative findings, contextualized through a qualitative synthesis of existing literature, reveal that relationship-seeking and entertainment are the dominant motivations, while hook-ups and validation are less prominent. These results challenge the common perception of dating apps as primarily facilitating casual encounters, highlighting instead the complex negotiation between personal gratification and socio-cultural constraints. The study underscores the evolving role of digital technologies in shaping relationship dynamics in conservative contexts and recommends further exploration through mixed method approaches with larger and more diverse samples to assess how gratifications are pursued and achieved.

INTRODUCTION

According to Naomi Baron, online and mobile technologies are reshaping communication, and relationships increasingly compete with digital media for attention (Baron, 2010). Until the early 2000s, most romantic relationships were formed offline. However, multiple studies now suggest that digital media has transformed communication by connecting people and facilitating relationships through social media and mobile dating applications (Valkenburg & Peter, 2007; Rizzo et al., 2019; Abbasi, 2019; Garris, 2020). The widespread use of smartphones has accelerated the shift from offline to online interaction, contributing to the continuous digitization of romantic relationships. Consequently, finding a partner has increasingly

become an online endeavor through mobile dating applications (Jung et al., 2019). Dating apps are often considered a Western phenomenon, dating app culture entered Pakistan around 2012 with the arrival of Tinder, and the number of regular users has continued to grow since then (Ahmad et al., 2016). Despite this growth, research on dating app use in Pakistan remains limited. One study found that both men and women use Tinder to satisfy different psychological and physical needs (Khan et al., 2019). Another explored why five popular dating apps, including Tinder, were banned by the Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (Khan, 2020). These studies indicate that the future of mobile dating apps in Pakistan remains uncertain due to the country's patriarchal and conservative social

structure. There is still limited understanding of why people use different dating apps (Chin et al., 2019), and previous research highlights the need for investigations across countries, as dating cultures vary significantly between societies (Danielsbacka et al., 2019).

This exploratory study aims to enhance understanding of mobile dating app use within the cultural context of Pakistan through the theoretical lens of the Uses and Gratifications framework. The central premise of this theory is that individuals actively choose certain forms of media to satisfy specific needs. To examine these motivations, this study employs the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale developed by Welch and Morgan (2018), which operationalizes Uses and Gratifications Theory for mobile dating contexts.

Literature Review

Digital Dating and Platform Affordances

Before widespread internet use, romantic partners were often introduced through family or social networks. However, online platforms, combined with algorithmic matching and big data, shifted partner search into digital spaces (Jung et al., 2019). Studies show that many romantic relationships in Western societies now begin online, especially among individuals limited by age, location, or sexual orientation (Chin et al., 2019).

Mobile dating apps further transformed dating practices by allowing constant connectivity through smartphones. These apps are generally location-based, easy to use, and allow users to choose partners based on compatibility. Compared to traditional dating websites, mobile apps simplify partner search and provide benefits such as access to people with similar interests or orientations, support for socially anxious users, and exposure to diverse social circles (Shetty et al., 2017). Many users also maintain profiles across multiple apps simultaneously (Jung et al., 2019; Broeker, 2021).

Most dating apps rely on profile browsing, swiping, and algorithmic matching. A mutual right swipe leads to a match and enables communication. Despite these shared features,

platforms differ in their purpose and social meaning.

Tinder is highly visual, with limited profile information, and is commonly associated with casual dating and hook-up culture (Lundquist & Curington, 2019). Bumble has been described as a “feminist app” because only women can initiate conversations after a match, giving them more control over interaction (Pruchniewska & Shah Hoque, 2020). Badoo emphasizes verified profiles and safety features, making it popular among users seeking authenticity and trust (Shetty et al., 2017). Muzmatch is designed specifically for Muslim users and incorporates religious considerations into its structure. Features such as blurred profile photos, initials instead of full names, and the option to include a family member in conversations are intended to accommodate religious norms while helping Muslims search for partners (Abubakar et al., 2020).

Uses and Gratifications Approach to Dating App Use

The Uses and Gratifications (U&G) approach explains why people actively choose particular media to meet specific needs. Rather than treating users as passive, this framework highlights their motivations and goals. In the context of dating apps, it helps explain why users seek emotional, social, or relational outcomes through digital platforms.

Welch and Morgan (2018) developed the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale, which identifies four main motivations for dating app use: validation, relationships, hook-ups, and entertainment. These categories are useful for examining dating app behavior across different contexts, including Pakistan.

Gratifications Sought Through Mobile Dating Apps

Validation

Validation refers to the desire for approval, affirmation, and recognition. Research suggests that receiving matches, profile views, and messages can improve users’ confidence and sociability (Jung et al., 2019; Haider, 2022). Validation is especially important for marginalized groups

because dating apps provide anonymity and reduce anxiety (Sumter & Vandenbosch, 2019). In Pakistan, where dating is socially stigmatized, validation may be an especially significant motivation.

Relationships

Seeking committed relationships is another major reason people use dating apps. These platforms allow users to search for partners based on personal preferences and make it easier to build emotional connections through mediated communication (Chin et al., 2019; Lundquist & Curington, 2019). Online interaction may also reduce the pressure of face-to-face encounters, particularly for individuals with dating anxiety (Valkenburg & Peter, 2007; Bryant & Sheldon, 2017). In Pakistan, where arranged marriage remains dominant, interest in self-selected relationships makes this motivation particularly relevant (Qureshi et al., 2014).

Hook-Ups

Dating apps, particularly Tinder, are often associated with casual sex and hook-up culture (Lundquist & Curington, 2019). Studies show that sexual gratification is a major motivation for many Tinder users, especially men (Ligtenberg, 2015; Lundquist & Curington, 2019; MacLeod & McArthur, 2019; Sumter et al., 2017; Timmermans & Courtois, 2018). However, this aspect has been studied less for apps such as Bumble, Muzmatch, and Badoo. In Pakistan's conservative context, it is important to examine whether such motivations exist in similar ways.

Entertainment

Entertainment is also a common motivation for dating app use. Users often browse profiles, chat, and create profiles for fun, distraction, or to reduce boredom (Sumter & Vandenbosch, 2019; Khan et al., 2019). Activities such as playful interaction and profile-building contribute to the entertainment value of these apps (Bryant & Sheldon, 2017; Bryden, 2017).

Socio-Cultural Constraints and Patriarchy in Pakistan

The motivations behind dating app use do not exist outside cultural context. Pakistan is widely characterized as a patriarchal society in which gender relations, intimacy, and marriage are structured through strong familial control and moral regulation. Interactions between unrelated men and women are often socially restricted, and self-selected relationships—particularly for women—may be stigmatized. Romantic relationships formed outside family approval are therefore frequently concealed or reframed to maintain social acceptability. These dynamics reinforce gendered power hierarchies and shape both offline and online relationship practices (Aksar et al., 2020).

Research further shows that patriarchal norms extend into digital environments. Women's participation in online spaces, including social media and dating platforms, is often influenced by surveillance, harassment, and reputational concerns, reflecting the continuation of offline gender restrictions in virtual settings (Aksar et al., 2020). Consequently, dating applications in Pakistan do not operate as neutral or liberating spaces but are embedded within broader socio-cultural structures.

Despite these constraints, the spread of smartphones and internet access has encouraged the use of dating apps among urban and educated youth in Pakistan. Platforms such as Tinder and Bumble are increasingly used in cities such as Islamabad, Lahore, and Karachi, creating new opportunities for cross-gender interaction that are often limited in offline settings (Khan, 2020; Sohail et al., 2024). These platforms provide semi-private spaces where users can interact with less direct family oversight.

From a Uses and Gratifications perspective, dating app use in Pakistan reflects active engagement driven by a range of social and psychological needs. Sohail et al. (2024) found that users engage with Tinder for companionship, emotional support, friendship, and sometimes sexual fulfillment. These motivations often overlap, suggesting that users navigate dating apps with multiple intentions rather than a single goal.

Complementing these findings, Bokhari, Sheikh, and Farooq (2025) examine dating culture among adolescents in Pakistan, using surveys and focus groups to explore engagement patterns. They find that dating influences intimacy, family dynamics, and behavioral risks, interpreting these behaviors through a moral lens that highlights religious and cultural concerns about “Western” lifestyles. While the study reflects value-laden assumptions, it provides empirical insight into the socio-cultural context shaping the adoption and negotiation of mobile dating applications in Pakistan.

Qualitative research among university students further shows that users often seek meaningful relationships, compatible partners, and broader social networks through dating apps (Nadeem, 2023). Participants also viewed the platforms as signs of changing social attitudes toward relationships and marriage, suggesting that digital platforms may be gradually reshaping ideas about intimacy in Pakistani society.

At the same time, the literature highlights considerable skepticism regarding dating apps as tools for long-term commitment or spouse selection. Recent national surveys show that despite the availability of dating or matchmaking apps, over 80% of Pakistanis still marry through arranged processes, demonstrating the continuing dominance of family-centered marriage structures (Gallup & Gilani, 2024). It indicates that while dating and matchmaking apps are increasingly used in Pakistan, many individuals remain skeptical of their reliability for serious long-term relationships. Instead, users often treat these platforms as temporary or exploratory spaces, with major relationship decisions still guided by family-centered marriage norms.

Similarly, Bajwa et al. (2024) found a strong association between dating app use and the rise of a “hookup culture” among Pakistani youth. Their findings suggest that many users prefer short-term relationships and use dating applications mainly for entertainment. However, this does not eliminate relationship-oriented uses; rather, it highlights the coexistence of different motivations within the same digital spaces.

Gender also shapes how dating apps are used and understood. Iqbal et al. (2025) show that Pakistani

women’s experiences on platforms such as Bumble involve both agency and constraint. Although features that allow women to initiate conversations may create a sense of control, users still face stigma, safety concerns, and fear of reputational damage. This demonstrates how patriarchal norms continue to influence digital courtship.

Overall, dating app culture in Pakistan can be understood as a hybrid and contested space. Users seek companionship, validation, entertainment, and sometimes long-term relationships, but these goals are shaped by social stigma, gendered expectations, and concerns about family acceptance. Rather than replacing traditional marriage systems, dating apps are often integrated into them, with users attempting to transform app-based relationships into socially acceptable forms. Collectively, these studies provide a strong foundation for applying the Uses and Gratifications Theory to understand Pakistani dating app users within a patriarchal and morally constrained socio-cultural environment.

Theoretical Framework

The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), introduced by Katz and Blumler in the early 1940s, conceptualizes media users as active agents who select communication technologies to satisfy specific psychological, emotional, and social needs (Katz et al., 1973; Blumler, 1979). The theory emphasizes that individuals engage with media intentionally rather than passively absorbing content, and that their motivations can be categorized into cognitive, personal, interactive, social integration, and escapism-related needs. Cognitive needs relate to seeking information; personal needs address emotional satisfaction and pleasure; interactive needs reflect self-esteem, confidence, and stability; social integration needs highlight the desire to stay connected with others; and escapism fulfills relaxation and diversion purposes. UGT’s central premise is that media users are capable of interpreting and incorporating media messages into their lives to satisfy these needs (Blumler, 1979).

While UGT provides a framework for media behavior, its application in Pakistan requires

situating the theory within a patriarchal social structure. Social norms, cultural expectations, and gendered restrictions limit offline opportunities for cross-gender interaction, making mobile dating apps an alternative space for pursuing social and emotional gratifications. Studies indicate that Pakistani dating app users often seek companionship, emotional validation, and relationship formation—needs that are difficult to fulfill openly due to societal constraints (Sohail et al., 2024). Use of these apps is moderated by concerns about honor, reputation, and family approval, resulting in a pattern in which users pursue personal gratification while cautiously navigating socially acceptable outcomes, particularly marriage. Women, in particular, negotiate agency and risk by seeking relational and emotional gratifications while managing potential stigma or harassment (Khan, 2020; Iqbal et al., 2025).

Integrating UGT with a patriarchal perspective therefore allows this study to explain not only why individuals use dating apps in Pakistan but also how social structures shape the nature, meaning, and consequences of their usage. This theoretical lens is particularly relevant for analyzing mobile dating applications such as Tinder, Bumble, Muzmatch, and Badoo. Motivations behind app usage reflect broader changes in social interaction, relational expectations, and media-mediated courtship in Pakistan. These motivations are operationalized in the present study using the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale, linking the theoretical framework directly to empirical measurement within a culturally specific context.

Methodology

This study employs a descriptive quantitative research design, utilizing the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale (Welch & Morgan, 2018) to examine the motivations of Pakistani users for engaging with mobile dating applications. Dating app usage was the dependent variable; gratifications (Validation, Relationships, Hook-Ups, and Entertainment) were treated as independent variables. Data were collected via anonymous online surveys, ensuring

confidentiality and allowing participants to opt out without consequence.

Participants and Sampling

Due to the sensitive nature of dating apps in Pakistan, recruiting a large sample was challenging. An exponential non-discriminative snowball sampling technique was employed, where initial participants referred others within their social networks (Dudovskiy, 2011). This approach is particularly suitable for hard-to-reach populations experiencing social stigma or taboo (Etikan, 2016). The study primarily targeted emerging adults aged 18–25, the demographic most likely to use dating apps (Sumter & Vandenberg, 2019). To broaden insight, respondents up to 40 years old were included. Most participants were single and university-educated, representing an urban segment of Pakistani society more open to Western-influenced digital dating practices.

Measurements

The Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale (Welch & Morgan, 2018) was employed using a five-point Likert scale (1 = **Strongly Disagree** to 5 = **Strongly Agree**). The scale assessed four key gratifications: Validation, Relationships, Hook-Ups, and Entertainment. Demographic information was collected on Hometown, Gender, Age, Education, Marital Status, and app usage habits.

Results & Findings

Participant Demographics

A total of 62 valid responses were collected from users across Pakistan. The majority were male (72.6%), with females representing 27.4% (Table 1). Most participants were from Islamabad (41.9%), followed by Lahore (8.1%), with smaller representation from Rawalpindi, Multan, Khanewal, Karachi, and Faisalabad (Table 2). Age distribution indicated that most respondents were emerging adults aged 18–25 (62.9%), followed by 26–30 years (30.6%) (Table 3). Educationally, 56.5% held undergraduate degrees, 27.4% had postgraduate qualifications, and 16.1% had completed high school (Table 4). Most participants were single (91.9%) (Table 5),

reflecting a sample primarily navigating early adult relationships within Pakistan’s socio-cultural context.

Table 1: Gender Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	45	72.6%
Female	17	27.4%
Total	62	100%

Table 2: Hometown Distribution

Hometown	Frequency	Percent
Islamabad	26	41.9%
Lahore	5	8.1%
Rawalpindi	3	4.8%
Multan	3	4.8%
Khanewal	3	4.8%
Karachi	3	4.8%
Faisalabad	3	4.8%
Other (Swabi, Gujrat, Mirpur AJK, etc.)	16	25.8%

Table 3: Age Distribution

Age Group	Frequency	Percent
18-25	39	62.9%
26-30	19	30.6%
31-35	3	4.8%
36-40	1	1.6%

Table 4: Education Levels

Education	Frequency	Percent
High School	10	16.1%
Undergraduate	35	56.5%
Postgraduate	17	27.4%

Table 5: Marital Status

Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	57	91.9%
Engaged	3	4.8%
Married	2	3.2%

Dating App Usage Patterns

Bumble emerged as the most frequently used app (19.4%), with equal preference for Tinder and Bumble (38.7%) (Table 6). Other apps, including Muzmatch and Badoo, were less commonly used. Most respondents reported using dating apps for

0-2 hours per day (88.7%), and 74.2% indicated they would stop using an app if it were banned, highlighting the influence of social acceptability, moral scrutiny, and local regulations on engagement.

Table 6: Usage Patterns

Variable	Tinder	Bumble	Muzmatch	Badoo	Other
Usage Frequency	5 (8.1%)	12 (19.4%)	1 (1.6%)	1 (1.6%)	19 (30.6%)
Preference	24 (38.7%)	24 (38.7%)	2 (3.2%)	2 (3.2%)	10 (16.1%)
Daily Usage 0-2 hours	55 (88.7%)	-	-	-	-
Would stop if banned	46 (74.2%)	-	-	-	-

Gratifications and Scale Reliability

The Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha

= 0.900), and factor analysis confirmed significant correlations among variables (Tables 7-8).

Table 7: Reliability Statistics

Scale	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items
Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale	0.900	0.902

Table 8: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Test	Value
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure	0.816
Bartlett's Test Approx. Chi-Square	786.730
df	120
Sig.	0.000

Descriptive Statistics of Gratification Variables

Descriptive statistics (Table 9) indicated that Entertainment (M = 3.42) and Relationships (M = 3.08) were the primary gratifications, while Hook-Ups (M = 2.57) and Validation (M = 2.48) were

secondary. Left-skewed distributions for Relationships, Entertainment, and Validation and right-skewed Hook-Ups suggest meaningful variability in engagement patterns.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of Gratifications

Variable	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis	Min	Max
Validation	2.476	2.50	1.00	1.017	-0.017	-0.899	1	5
Relationships	3.081	3.167	3.67	1.137	-0.219	-0.945	1	5
Hook-Ups	2.573	2.25	1.00	1.359	0.480	-1.113	1	5
Entertainment	3.416	3.60	3.40	1.165	-0.778	-0.250	1	5

The study collected 62 valid responses from Pakistani dating app users, with males constituting 72.6% and females 27.4%. Most participants were from Islamabad (41.9%), followed by Lahore, Rawalpindi, and other urban centers. Emerging adults aged 18–25 were the dominant age group (62.9%), followed by 26–30-year-olds, reflecting both global digital dating trends and the concentration of younger adults in Pakistan's urban, educated population. Educationally, the majority held undergraduate degrees (56.5%), with postgraduate and high school qualifications representing smaller proportions. Most participants were single (91.9%), suggesting that the sample largely consists of individuals navigating early adult relationships within Pakistan's socio-cultural context.

Analysis of dating app usage revealed that Bumble was the most frequently used platform (19.4%), while Tinder and Bumble were equally preferred (38.7%). Other platforms, such as Muzmatch and Badoo, were less commonly used. Most respondents engaged with apps for 0–2 hours per day (88%), and 74.2% indicated they would stop using an app if banned. These patterns highlight the influence of moral scrutiny, legal uncertainty, and social expectations on app engagement.

Gratification analysis using the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale (Welch & Morgan, 2018) indicated that Relationship ($M = 3.08$) and Entertainment ($M = 3.42$) gratifications were most prominent. Hook-Ups ($M = 2.57$) and Validation ($M = 2.48$) were secondary. Skewness in the distributions suggests meaningful variability in user motivations, with Relationships, Entertainment, and Validation left-skewed and Hook-Ups right-skewed.

These gratifications are pursued within the constraints of Pakistan's patriarchal social

structure. Relationship-seeking was central, with users balancing emotional connection with considerations of family approval, social acceptability, and potential marriage. Women in particular navigated these apps cautiously, reflecting reputational concerns and potential family scrutiny. Entertainment motivations operated largely in private or semi-anonymous spaces, offering social interaction, distraction, and leisure within culturally permissible boundaries. Hook-Up and Validation motivations were secondary, reflecting the moderating effects of conservative norms and gendered expectations. Qualitative responses further revealed a dual-use pattern: participants pursued personal gratification while simultaneously ensuring adherence to social norms, indicating that app engagement involves continuous negotiation between individual desires and societal expectations.

Discussion

The study captured dating app use among young adults in Pakistan, with emerging adults dominating the sample and males overrepresented, consistent with broader digital dating trends (Sumter & Vandenbosch, 2019). Most participants were single and urban, reflecting individuals navigating early adult relationships within culturally conservative contexts.

Bumble emerged as the most frequently used platform, though Tinder was equally preferred by many respondents. Other apps, including Muzmatch and Badoo, were less commonly used. Daily engagement was generally limited to 0–2 hours, highlighting cautious participation shaped by moral scrutiny, societal expectations, and platform availability (Khan, 2020).

Analysis of gratifications revealed that relationship-seeking and entertainment were the primary motivations. Users engaged with apps for emotionally meaningful connections and enjoyable interactions, while casual sexual gratification and validation were less central. Variability in responses suggests that motivations are influenced by personal factors and social norms.

Gratifications were clearly pursued within Pakistan's patriarchal context. Relationship-oriented use required balancing emotional connection with family expectations and social approval. Women, in particular, navigated apps cautiously due to reputational concerns and potential scrutiny (Iqbal et al., 2025). Entertainment served as a socially acceptable outlet for leisure, distraction, and semi-anonymous social interaction. Motivations related to Hook-Ups and Validation remained secondary, reflecting conservative cultural norms and gendered expectations (Khan et al., 2019; Arnett & Tanner, 2006). Qualitative responses indicated that users continuously negotiated personal gratification against social acceptability.

Contrary to the prevailing narrative emphasizing casual sexual encounters (Bajwa et al., 2024), the findings show that relationship-oriented goals coexist with entertainment and social motivations. Users pursue companionship, emotional support, and potential long-term partnerships, underscoring the complexity of dating apps used in socially conservative settings and aligning with Uses and Gratifications Theory.

Methodological insights emerged alongside these findings: hesitation, withdrawal, and reluctance to discuss experiences reflected the stigma associated with dating in conservative contexts. Snowball sampling was necessary to access this hidden population, revealing not only methodological considerations but also the substantive influence of social stigma on user behavior. Integrating these insights here demonstrates that participant behavior and engagement cannot be fully understood without accounting for the sensitivities of recruitment and social pressures.

Overall, dating app use in Pakistan operates as a negotiated social space where individuals pursue

multiple gratifications while managing social, cultural, and familial expectations. Relationship-oriented motivations dominate, yet entertainment, personal exploration, and identity management remain important. These findings extend Uses and Gratifications Theory to a culturally specific context, showing how social structures shape digital behaviors.

Conclusion

This study provides a nuanced understanding of dating app use in Pakistan, revealing how users actively pursue gratifications while navigating the constraints of a patriarchal social structure. Relationship-oriented motivations emerged as the most prominent, reflecting the importance of emotional intimacy and long-term connections even within a context marked by social stigma and familial oversight. Entertainment also played a significant role, offering private spaces for social interaction, distraction, and experimentation. Motivations such as Hook-Ups and Validation were less central, highlighting the moderating influence of cultural, religious, and gendered norms on app engagement.

The findings demonstrate that dating app use in Pakistan cannot be reduced to a simple "hook-up culture" narrative; instead, users engage in complex, multi-dimensional behaviors that balance personal desires, social expectations, and cultural constraints. Methodologically, recruitment challenges underscore the sensitivity and hidden nature of this population, providing insights that extend beyond traditional survey data.

By situating Uses and Gratifications Theory within the Pakistani socio-cultural context, this study contributes to both theory and practice. It highlights how digital platforms operate as negotiated social spaces where gratification, relationship-building, and cultural considerations coexist. Future research should explore gendered differences, regional variations, and comparisons between gratifications sought versus obtained to further deepen understanding. Practically, these insights can inform platform design that respects privacy, cultural norms, and gendered experiences,

enhancing user engagement in socially sensitive environments.

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References

- Abbasi, I. S. (2019). Social media addiction in romantic relationships: Does user's age influence vulnerability to social media infidelity? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 139, 277-280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2018.10.038>
- Aksar, I. A., Firdaus, A. S. B., Danaee, M., & Maqsood, H. (2020). Virtual manifestations of patriarchy: Digital experience of Pakistani women. *Asian Women*, 36(1), 61-89. <https://doi.org/10.14431/aw.2020.3.36.1.61>
- Abubakar, A., Irdina, N., Noorani, M., Syafiqah, U., & Rashidi, M. (2020). Understanding Muslims Self-Presentation Strategies in Online Dating. In *International Journal on Perceptive and Cognitive Computing (IJPCC)* (Vol. 6, Issue 2).
- Ahmad, S., Mustafa, M., & Ullah, A. (2016). Association of demographics, motives and intensity of using Social Networking Sites with the formation of bonding and bridging social capital in Pakistan. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 57, 107-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.12.027>
- Arnett, J. J., & Tanner, J. L. (2006). *Emerging Adults in America* book. American Psychological Association.
- Bokhari, S. S. S., Sheikh, J. A., & Farooq, S. (2025). Dating culture in Pakistani society and its adverse effects upon adolescents in the perspective of prevalent technology and innovations.
- Bajwa, S. E., Waheed, S., & Bhatti, T. F. (2024). Investigating the impact of mobile dating applications in perspective of hookup culture among Pakistani youth. HN Publisher.
- Baron, N. S. (2010). *Always On: Language in an Online and Mobile World*. In *Always On: Language in an Online and Mobile World*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195313055.001.0001>
- Blumler, J. G. (1979). The role of theory in uses and gratifications studies. *Communication Research*, 6(1), 9-36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009365027900600102>
- Broeker, F. (2021). 'We went from the anonymity of the internet into my private WhatsApp': Rituals of transition among dating app users in Berlin. *New Media and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448211029200>
- Bryant, K., & Sheldon, P. (2017). Cyber Dating in the Age of Mobile Apps: Understanding Motives, Attitudes, and Characteristics of Users. *American Communication Journal*, 19(2).
- Bryden, L. T. (2017). *Online Dating Applications and the Uses and Gratifications Theory* [Eastern Washington University]. <http://dc.ewu.edu/theses/453>
- Chin, K., Edelstein, R. S., & Vernon, P. A. (2019). Attached to dating apps: Attachment orientations and preferences for dating apps. *Mobile Media and Communication*, 7(1), 41-59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2050157918770696>
- Danielsbacka, M., Tanskanen, A. O., & Billari, F. C. (2019). Who meets online? Personality traits and sociodemographic characteristics associated with online partnering in Germany. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 143, 139-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2019.02.024>

- Dudovskiy, J. (2011). Snowball sampling. *Research-Methodology.Net*.
<https://research-methodology.net/sampling-in-primary-data-collection/snowball-sampling/>
- Etikan, I. (2016). Comparison of Snowball Sampling and Sequential Sampling Technique. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 3(1).
<https://doi.org/10.15406/bbij.2016.03.00055>
- Finkel, E. J., Eastwick, P. W., Karney, B. R., Reis, H. T., & Sprecher, S. (2012). Online Dating: A Critical Analysis From the Perspective of Psychological Science. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest, Supplement*, 13(1), 3–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100612436522>
- Gallup & Gilani Pakistan. (2024, August 23). Among married Pakistanis, 4 out of 5 (81%) have an arranged marriage. Gallup Pakistan. <https://www.gallup.com.pk/>
- Garris, B. R. (2020). Modern Love: You, Me, and Smartphone Makes Three. *Marriage and Family Review*, 56(4), 343–368.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01494929.2020.1712574>
- Haider, S. B. (2022). Swiping for love: Inside the world of online dating in Pakistan.
- Iqbal, N., Mohd, N., Shaari, A., & Azhar, K. (2025). Swiping against the norm: Pakistani women's experiences on Bumble through a technofeminist lens. *Gender, Technology and Development*, 29.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09718524.2025.2546278>
- Jung, J., Bapna, R., Ramaprasad, J., & Umyarov, A. (2019a). Love Unshackled: Identifying the Effect of Mobile App Adoption in Online Dating. *MIS Quarterly*, 43, 47–72.
- Khan, Ahmed, A. (2020). Effect of Online Dating apps on Karachi Based Youth. *Pakistan Journal of Media Science*, 1(1).
- Katz, E., Gurevitch, M., & Haas, H. (1973). On the Use of the Mass Media for Important Things.
https://repository.upenn.edu/asc_papers/267
- Khan, M. H., Syeda, A. S., Mahmood, Q., & Gull, Z. (2019). Tinder use among pakistani adults: a socio-psychological need perspective. *JURNAL STUDI KOMUNIKASI*, 3, 316–331.
<https://doi.org/10.25139/jsk.3i3.1954>
- Ligtenberg, L. (2015). Tinder, the App That is Setting the Dating Scene on Fire: A Uses and Gratifications Perspective.
- Lundquist, J. H., & Curington, C. V. (2019). Love Me Tinder, Love Me Sweet. *Contexts*, 18(4), 22–27.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1536504219883848>
- MacLeod, C., & McArthur, V. (2019). The construction of gender in dating apps: an interface analysis of Tinder and Bumble. *Feminist Media Studies*, 19(6), 822–840.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2018.1494618>
- Nadeem, F. (2023). Exploring the usage of dating apps in educational youth of Pakistan: Experiences and perception (Unpublished thesis). University of Management and Technology, Lahore.
- Pruchniewska, U., & Shah Hoque, A. (2020). "I Like That It's My Choice a Couple Different Times": Gender, Affordances, and User Experience on Bumble Dating Cite this paper Related papers Programming Sex, Gender, and Sexuality: Infrastructural Failures in the "Feminist " Dating App <http://ijoc.org>.
- Qureshi, K., Charsley, K., & Shaw, A. (2014). Marital instability among British Pakistanis: Transnationality, conjugalities and Islam. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 37(2), 261–279.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2012.720691>
- Rizzo, C. J., Collibee, C., Nugent, N. R., & Armeiy, M. F. (2019). Let's Get Digital: Understanding Adolescent Romantic Relationships Using Naturalistic Assessments of Digital Communication. *Child Development Perspectives*, 13(2),

- 104-109.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12320>
- Sohail, S. A., Mahmood, Q., Khan, M. H., & Gull, Z. (2019). Tinder use among Pakistani adults: A socio-psychological need perspective. *Jurnal Studi Komunikasi*, 3(3), 316-331.
<https://doi.org/10.25139/jsk.v3i3.1954>
- Shetty, R., Grispos, G., & Choo, K.-K. R. (2017). Are You Dating Danger? An Interdisciplinary Approach to Evaluating the (In)Security of Android Dating Apps. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Computing*, 6(2), 197-207.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/tsusc.2017.2783858>
- Sumter, S. R., & Vandenbosch, L. (2019). Dating gone mobile: Demographic and personality-based correlates of using smartphone-based dating applications among emerging adults. *New Media and Society*, 21(3), 655-673.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818804773>
- Sumter, S. R., Vandenbosch, L., & Ligtenberg, L. (2017). Love me Tinder: Untangling emerging adults' motivations for using the dating application Tinder. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(1), 67-78.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2016.04.009>
- Timmermans, E., & Courtois, C. (2018). From swiping to casual sex and/or committed relationships: Exploring the experiences of Tinder users. *Information Society*, 34(2), 59-70.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01972243.2017.1414093>
- Timmermans, E., & de Caluwé, E. (2017). Development and validation of the Tinder Motives Scale (TMS). *Computers in Human Behavior*, 70, 341-350.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.01.028>
- Valkenburg, P. M., & Peter, J. (2007a). Who visits online dating sites? Exploring some characteristics of online daters. *Cyberpsychology and Behavior*, 10(6), 849-852.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2007.9941>
- Welch, J. R., & Morgan, M. (2018). Development and Validation of the Mobile Dating App Gratification Scale: Effects of Sought Gratifications on User Behavior and Outcomes. *Communication, Society and Media*, 1(2), 108.
<https://doi.org/10.22158/csm.v1n2p108>